

Teacher Transition from Private to Public Schools

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how teachers in Silay City, Negros Occidental experienced the transition from private to public schools, an area in which local evidence remains limited. Specifically, it investigated the extent of changes in school administration and policy, pay and benefits, job security, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments, as well as the challenges, opportunities, coping strategies, and implications of the transition for instructional practice and well-being. An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was employed. In Phase I, quantitative data were collected from 102 teachers who had transitioned from private to public schools across 22 public elementary, secondary, and integrated schools. In Phase II, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 15 purposively selected teachers to explain and enrich the quantitative findings. Results showed a very high overall extent of change in the transition experience (grand mean = 4.48). The highest-rated areas were pay and benefits (M = 4.61), job security (M = 4.57), interpersonal relations (M = 4.53), and school administration and policy (M = 4.47), while work assignments (M = 4.34) and work conditions (M = 4.33) remained comparatively lower, though still described as very high change. Qualitative findings revealed that teachers viewed public school employment as more secure, better compensated, and more supportive of professional growth. However, they also encountered bureaucratic demands, larger class sizes, limited resources, heavier workloads, and emotional strain during the early months of transition. To cope with these demands, teachers relied on time management, peer mentoring, emotional support, and continuous professional development. The study concludes that a Transition Support Plan featuring structured onboarding, mentorship, resource provision, workload management, and psychosocial support is necessary to promote teacher well-being and sustain successful transition outcomes in public schools.

Keywords: Teacher Transition, Private to Public Schools, Transition Support Plan, Workplace Adaptation

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INTRODUCTION

The movement of teachers from private to public schools has become an increasingly visible pattern in the Philippine education system. Recent Philippine studies indicate that this shift is shaped by differences in compensation, benefits, employment stability, workload expectations, administrative support, and opportunities for career advancement across school sectors. National and regional data underscore this trend. Maligalig et al. (2021) reported that more than one-fifth (21%) of private school teachers in urban and semi-urban areas had transitioned to public school systems, largely because of salary disparities, job insecurity, and limited opportunities for career advancement. Similarly, David and Santos (2023) found that in several divisions across the country, the proportion of teachers moving from private to public schools increased by 18% to 25% over the past five years, particularly in contexts where private schools faced resource shortages, high workloads, and inconsistent administrative practices. These patterns suggest that public-school positions are often perceived as more attractive because they offer more stable employment, standardized compensation, government benefits, and clearer opportunities for professional growth than many private-school appointments. At the same time, the shift involves more than a change of employer; it also requires adjustment to a different organizational culture, policy environment, instructional context, and professional role.

For teachers, this transition brings both opportunity and strain. Public schools may provide stronger job security, broader access to professional development, and more formalized systems of support. However, they may also require adaptation to more bureaucratic administrative procedures, larger class sizes, heavier documentation, limited instructional resources, and more diverse learner needs. These realities matter because teacher transition affects not only teachers' adjustment and well-being but also the continuity of instruction, classroom climate, and institutional stability of receiving schools. In Negros Occidental, this issue is especially relevant because division records and school hiring patterns suggest that a growing segment of newly hired public-school teachers consists of transferees from private institutions, prompting local interest in how these teachers adapt to their new professional contexts.

Although recent Philippine studies have examined teacher transition from private to public schools, most have focused on qualitative or phenomenological accounts of teachers' motivations, challenges, and adjustment experiences. While these studies provide valuable insights, they offer limited localized evidence from smaller divisions such as Silay City, where school culture, leadership practices, learner demographics, and resource access may shape transition differently. They also do not sufficiently integrate measurable patterns of transition with teachers' lived experiences. Consequently, findings from broader national or regional contexts cannot be assumed to reflect the realities of teachers in the Division of Silay City.

The problem addressed in this study is the lack of context-specific evidence on how teachers who transfer from private to public schools in Silay City experience changes in school administration and policy, pay and benefits, job security, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments, as well as the challenges, opportunities, coping strategies, and implications for instructional practice and well-being associated with this transition. Without such localized evidence, school leaders and policymakers have limited empirical basis for designing interventions and support systems that can ease adjustment, strengthen teacher integration, and improve retention in the public-school system.

Accordingly, this study examined the experiences of teachers who transferred from private to public schools in Silay City, guided by six transition dimensions adapted from the attrition factors identified by Ortega-Dela Cruz (2016) and reinforced by recent Philippine studies on teacher transition. Using an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, the study generated localized evidence on both measurable patterns and lived experiences. Specifically, the quantitative phase involved 102 transitioning teachers drawn from a population of 137 across 22 public elementary, secondary, and integrated schools in the Division of Silay City, while the qualitative phase included 15 purposively selected teachers. By integrating quantitative and qualitative evidence, the study extends earlier qualitative research and provides an evidence-based foundation for a Transition Support Plan to strengthen teacher onboarding, mentoring, workload support, and institutional assistance in the public-school system.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to examine the transition of teachers from private to public schools in Silay City.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of changes that teachers transitioning from private to public schools experience in the following areas?
 - 1.1 School administration and policy
 - 1.2 Pay & benefits
 - 1.3 Job security

1.4 Interpersonal relations

1.5 Work conditions

1.6 Work assignments

2. What are the challenges encountered by teachers transitioning from private to public schools?
3. What opportunities arise for teachers transitioning from private to public schools?
4. What coping strategies do teachers employ during the transition process?
5. What are the implications of transitions on teachers' instructional practices and well-being?
6. Based on the quantitative and qualitative findings, what Transition Support Plan may be developed to assist teachers transitioning from private to public schools?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teacher transition from private to public schools is increasingly recognized as a multidimensional process shaped by economic, organizational, and relational conditions rather than by compensation alone. In the Philippine context, this process can be systematically understood through six key dimensions: school administration and policy, pay and benefits, job security, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments which together capture both the motivations for transfer and the dynamics of post-transfer adjustment. These dimensions serve as the core analytical framework of the present study, allowing for a more integrated examination of teacher mobility and adaptation.

Recent Philippine studies indicate that teachers are often drawn to public schools by stronger compensation, greater employment stability, and clearer opportunities for career advancement (Gonzales et al., 2021; David & Santos, 2023; Ostia & Celesio, 2025). In this regard, pay and benefits and job security emerge consistently as primary drivers of transition. However, the literature also suggests that these economic incentives alone do not guarantee a positive transition experience. While they explain why teachers move, they do not fully account for how teachers adjust after transfer. This distinction highlights a critical analytical insight: the factors that attract teachers to public schools are not necessarily the same factors that sustain their effectiveness and well-being once they enter the system.

This gap between motivation and adjustment is clarified by the study's theoretical foundations. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory explains why pay and benefits, job security, and aspects of work conditions function as hygiene factors that reduce dissatisfaction and make public-school positions more attractive. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs extends this explanation by emphasizing that teachers also seek higher-level outcomes such as professional recognition, career advancement, and self-actualization. In contrast, Schlossberg's Transition Theory shifts the focus from motivation to adaptation by highlighting the importance of situational context, personal resources, support systems, and coping strategies. When considered together, these frameworks provide a coherent explanation of the six transition dimensions: Herzberg and Maslow primarily explain movement into the public sector, while Schlossberg explains how teachers navigate changes in school administration and policy, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments after transfer. Thus, the theories are not treated as abstract constructs but as explanatory mechanisms directly linked to the variables of the study.

Empirical literature further demonstrates that post-transfer experiences are shaped less by the decision to move and more by the institutional conditions encountered after entry. Teachers who transition to public schools often face more formalized administrative procedures, heavier documentation requirements, larger class sizes, limited resources, and more diverse learner needs compared to their previous private-school contexts (Maligalig et al., 2021; David & Santos, 2023; Polinar & Gemota, 2025). These changes correspond directly to school administration and policy, work conditions, and work assignments, and can disrupt established instructional routines and professional confidence. However, the literature consistently shows that these challenges are mediated by the level of institutional support available. Administrative clarity, mentoring, collegial trust, and professional development opportunities have been associated with stronger adjustment, higher satisfaction, and improved retention (Haveman et al., 2024; Sayman et al., 2025). This suggests that teacher transition should be conceptualized not only as an individual adaptation process but also as a function of organizational responsiveness.

Importantly, the literature indicates that the six transition dimensions operate as an interconnected system rather than as isolated variables. School administration and policy shape role clarity and expectations, while interpersonal relations influence social integration and access to support. At the same time, work conditions and work assignments affect workload, stress, and teaching effectiveness. Recent studies on coping and professional adaptation further highlight the role of mentoring, peer networks, and continuous professional learning in facilitating successful transition (Maekele et al., 2023; Janairo & Capellan, 2024; Rivera & Delos Reyes, 2025). These findings underscore that successful transition is not determined by a single favorable factor. A teacher may benefit from improved compensation and job security yet still experience difficulty if administrative systems are unclear,

workloads are excessive, or collegial support is limited. Consequently, understanding teacher transition requires examining how these dimensions interact to shape overall experience.

Despite the growing body of research, two key limitations remain. First, many recent Philippine studies rely primarily on qualitative or phenomenological approaches, offering rich insights into teachers' lived experiences but limited evidence on the measurable extent of change across the six transition dimensions. Second, there is a lack of division-level research in smaller local contexts such as Silay City, where variations in school culture, leadership practices, resource availability, and learner demographics may significantly influence transition outcomes. As a result, findings from broader national or regional studies cannot be readily generalized to these settings. The present study addresses these gaps by employing a mixed-methods design that integrates quantitative and qualitative evidence to examine both the extent and nature of teacher transition in Silay City, and by translating these findings into an evidence-based Transition Support Plan.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, consisting of a quantitative phase followed by a qualitative phase. This design was appropriate because the study aimed to first measure the extent of teachers' transition experiences across six key dimensions and subsequently explain and contextualize these findings through participants' experiences. The quantitative phase generated general patterns of change, while the qualitative phase provided deeper insights into the challenges, opportunities, coping strategies, and implications associated with the transition. This sequential approach enabled a more comprehensive understanding of teacher transition by integrating statistical patterns with contextualized narratives.

Participants and Sampling

For the quantitative phase, proportional stratified sampling was employed to ensure adequate representation across school levels. From a population of 137 teachers who transitioned from private to public schools, a sample of 102 was determined using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator. Participants were drawn from 22 public elementary, secondary, and integrated schools, with proportional allocation across subgroups to capture variation in experiences.

For the qualitative phase, purposive sampling was used. Fifteen teachers were selected based on their quantitative responses, representing low, moderate, and high levels of transition experience. This approach ensured the inclusion of diverse perspectives and enabled an in-depth exploration of the transition process.

Instrument Validity and Reliability

A self-developed questionnaire was utilized to measure six transition dimensions: school administration and policy, pay and benefits, job security, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments. Content validity was established through expert evaluation by specialists in educational management and teacher training. The instrument was reviewed for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives, and revisions were made accordingly.

Reliability was assessed through pilot testing with 30 teachers outside the study sample. Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was secured from relevant school authorities, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. The instrument yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.85, indicating high internal consistency.

Data Collection

Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained permission from the appropriate school authorities and ensured that all participants provided informed consent. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any time.

Quantitative data were collected through an online survey administered via Google Forms to 102 participants, with printed copies provided when necessary to ensure accessibility.

Qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with 15 selected participants. Interviews were audio-recorded with consent and transcribed verbatim to facilitate analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure

Quantitative Analysis

Quantitative survey data from 102 teachers were coded, tabulated, and analyzed using mean scores and standard deviations to determine the extent of changes across the six transition dimensions and the variability of respondents' perceptions.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean scores and standard deviations, to determine the extent of changes experienced across the six transition dimensions.

To ensure interpretability, the following Likert scale was used:

Table 1

Scale interpretation for the quantitative phase

Mean Range	Description of Change
4.21 – 5.00	Very High Change
3.41 – 4.20	High Change
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Change
1.81 – 2.60	Low Change
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Change

Qualitative Analysis

Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following a systematic coding process: (1) familiarization through repeated reading of transcripts; (2) initial coding of meaningful data segments; (3) development of themes by grouping related codes; and (4) refinement of themes to ensure alignment with the research objectives.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the findings, the study employed:

- Triangulation, by comparing qualitative findings with quantitative results
- Member checking, through participant validation of interpretations
- Audit trail, documenting coding decisions and theme development

Table 2

Data analysis framework

Objective	Data Source	Analysis	Output
Assess the extent of perceived change across the six transition dimensions	Survey of 102 teachers	Means, standard deviations, and rank ordering	Descriptive profile of transition patterns
Explain the challenges and opportunities encountered during transition	Semi-structured interviews with 15 teachers	Thematic analysis (coding, categorizing, theme development)	Thematic explanation of transition experience
Identify coping strategies and implications for instructional practice and well-being	Interview transcripts and supporting survey trends	Thematic analysis (coding, categorizing, theme development)	Adaptation strategies and implications
Derive an empirically grounded Transition Support Plan	Integrated quantitative and qualitative findings	Side-by-side comparison and joint interpretation	Actionable school-level and division-level support components

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Phases

Integration was conducted during the interpretation stage, where qualitative findings were used to explain and elaborate on quantitative results. The quantitative phase identified the extent of changes during the transition, while the qualitative phase clarified the underlying reasons and contextual factors.

For example, high ratings in pay and benefits and job security were supported by participants' accounts of improved financial stability and career security, whereas comparatively lower ratings in work conditions were explained by increased workload and resource limitations. This integration ensured that findings were both statistically grounded and contextually meaningful.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to established ethical standards in research. Permission to conduct the study was obtained from relevant school authorities prior to data collection. Participants were provided with informed consent, ensuring awareness of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality was strictly maintained through data anonymization and secure storage of all collected information. No identifying details were included in reports or publications.

Measures were taken to minimize potential risks, including providing participants with access to support resources when needed. The researcher-maintained objectivity and integrity throughout the research process by ensuring transparency and minimizing potential bias.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that the transition from private to public schools is generally perceived as beneficial; however, this perception is not uniform across all dimensions. While teachers reported strong improvements in structural factors such as compensation and job security, comparatively lower ratings in work conditions and assignments suggest that the transition also introduces operational challenges. Qualitative findings further reveal that these gains are accompanied by increased workload, bureaucratic demands, and emotional strain, highlighting the transition as a complex and multi-layered process rather than a uniformly positive experience.

The Quantitative Findings section presents the statistical analysis of the survey data collected from 102 teachers who transitioned from private to public schools. The survey assessed teachers' perceptions across six key areas: school administration and policy, pay and benefits, job security, interpersonal relations, work conditions, and work assignments. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to quantify the teachers' experiences and to identify significant trends and variations in their perceptions of the changes they encountered during the transition.

Table 3

Summary of overall means across key areas

Key Area	Overall Mean	Interpretation
School Administration and Policy	4.47	Very High Change
Pay and Benefits	4.61	Very High Change
Job Security	4.57	Very High Change
Interpersonal Relations	4.53	Very High Change
Work Conditions	4.33	Very High Change
Work Assignments	4.34	Very High Change
Grand Mean	4.48	Very High Change

All six domains were interpreted within the upper range of the scale. This supports the description of the transition as generally advantageous, but the consistency of high means should not be read uncritically. Respondents were comparing public-school employment with prior private-school experience, so high scores reflect perceived improvement rather than the absence of problems. The ranking of means also matters: the strongest gains were concentrated in structural factors such as pay and benefits

($M = 4.61$), job security ($M = 4.57$), and interpersonal relations ($M = 4.53$), whereas the lowest-rated areas were work assignments ($M = 4.34$) and work conditions ($M = 4.33$). The 0.28-point spread between the highest and lowest domain means suggests that the transition was favorable but uneven, improving structural conditions more than everyday implementation.

Overall, the transition from private to public schools appears structurally advantageous but operationally demanding, characterized by strong gains in financial stability and job security alongside persistent challenges in workload, classroom conditions, and task demands, a pattern also noted in recent studies on teacher transition in the Philippine context (Gonzales et al., 2021; Ostia & Celesio, 2025). From the perspective of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, the highest-rated dimensions, pay and benefits and job security function as hygiene factors, effectively reducing dissatisfaction but not eliminating workplace challenges. In line with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, the findings indicate that teachers' basic and security needs are largely fulfilled; however, lower ratings in work conditions and assignments suggest that higher-level needs related to well-being and professional satisfaction remain partially unmet.

Consistent with Schlossberg's Transition Theory, the variation across dimensions highlights that successful adaptation depends on the availability of support systems. Lower-rated operational dimensions indicate that adjustment is ongoing and influenced by contextual and institutional factors.

1. School Administration and Policy

The first area examined was school administration and policy, focusing on teachers' perceptions of changes in administrative rules, regulations, and policies after transitioning from private to public schools. The findings show significant improvements in these areas.

Table 4

Extent of Changes in School Administration and Policy

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Policy Explanation	4.49	0.700	Very High Change
Administrative Support	4.35	0.792	Very High Change
Role Guidance	4.41	0.800	Very High Change
Expectations	4.48	0.685	Very High Change
Timely Communication	4.39	0.810	Very High Change
Clarification Support	4.46	0.753	Very High Change
Concern Resolution	4.58	0.724	Very High Change
Policy Updates	4.63	0.644	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.47		Very High Change

Teachers reported a very high extent of change in school administration and policy ($M = 4.47$), indicating that the transition to public schools involved substantial adjustments in rules, procedures, and communication practices. The highest ratings for policy updates and concern resolution suggest that teachers perceived stronger formal communication and procedural responsiveness in the public school system. However, the comparatively lower mean for administrative support indicates that support may not have been experienced as equally consistent across schools.

The moderate variability in responses further suggests that school-level leadership and implementation practices likely shaped teachers' experiences of adjustment. These findings are consistent with previous studies emphasizing the role of clear communication, effective leadership, and administrative support in facilitating teacher adjustment and professional functioning (Leithwood et al., 2022; Sebullen & Jimenez, 2024), and they align with Schlossberg's Transition Theory, which highlights institutional support as a key factor in successful adaptation during transition (Schlossberg, 1981).

2. Pay and Benefits

The second area examined was pay and benefits, which included changes in salary, allowances, and other benefits provided by the public school system. Teachers reported significant improvements in their pay and benefits upon transitioning.

Table 5

Extent of Changes in Pay and Benefits

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Salary Increase	4.68	0.566	Very High Change
Benefits & Security	4.63	0.596	Very High Change
Financial Stability	4.52	0.700	Very High Change
Benefits for Adaptation	4.52	0.714	Very High Change
Adequate Financial Support	4.56	0.698	Very High Change
Fair Compensation	4.70	0.672	Very High Change
Compensation vs. Job Demands	4.67	0.635	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.61		Very High Change

Teachers reported a very high extent of change in pay and benefits, with an overall mean of 4.61, indicating that financial improvement was one of the strongest outcomes of the transition to public schools. The highest-rated indicators were fair compensation (M = 4.70) and salary increase (M = 4.68), showing that teachers clearly recognized the financial advantages of public school employment. The relatively close mean scores and low standard deviation values also suggest that these positive perceptions were broadly shared among respondents. However, the slightly lower ratings for financial stability and benefits for adaptation imply that although compensation improved, financial gains alone did not fully remove the difficulties of adjustment.

From a theoretical perspective, this aligns with Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory, where salary and benefits operate as hygiene factors that reduce dissatisfaction but do not necessarily enhance long-term motivation. Similarly, under Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs, improvements in financial stability address teachers’ basic and security needs, but do not fully account for higher-level concerns such as professional fulfillment and well-being. Despite strong financial gains, teachers continue to report challenges related to workload and work conditions. This suggests that economic improvement alone is insufficient to ensure a fully positive transition experience.

3. Job Security

The third area, job security, assessed teachers' perceptions of employment stability, tenure, and the risk of termination in the public school system. Teachers felt significantly more secure in their positions after transitioning to public schools.

Table 6

Extent of Changes in Job Security

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Employment Security	4.75	0.455	Very High Change
Orientation on Job Status	4.56	0.683	Very High Change
Understanding Terms & Conditions	4.49	0.714	Very High Change
Performance & Promotion	4.51	0.700	Very High Change
Job Protection Policies	4.59	0.619	Very High Change
Fair Application of Rules	4.34	1.058	Very High Change
Transparent Decisions	4.48	1.012	Very High Change
Employment Stability	4.86	0.399	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.57		Very High Change

Teachers felt very high changes in job security, with the highest mean for Employment Stability (4.86). This indicates that teachers felt much more secure in their positions within the public school system, confirming the stability offered by public sector employment. The highest ratings for employment stability indicate that public schools provide a consistent and reliable sense of job permanence, which is a major shift from the relatively uncertain conditions in private institutions. In contrast, comparatively lower ratings in fairness and transparency suggest that while security is structurally strong, institutional processes governing decision-making may not be uniformly experienced. The relatively higher standard deviation values in these areas further indicate variation across school contexts, suggesting that governance practices and administrative fairness may differ depending on leadership and institutional culture.

These findings suggest that public school employment offers strong structural security, but perceptions of fairness and transparency are influenced by school-level implementation and governance practices, consistent with recent findings on teachers moving from private to public schools (Ostia & Celesio, 2025). From a theoretical perspective, this aligns with Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, where job security functions as a hygiene factor that reduces dissatisfaction. However, variability in fairness-related indicators suggests that organizational practices still shape overall satisfaction.

4. Interpersonal Relations

The interpersonal relations area focused on teachers' relationships with colleagues and administrators. Teachers reported significant improvements in collaboration and support after transitioning to public schools.

Table 7

Extent of Changes in Interpersonal Relations

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Welcomed by Colleagues	4.61	0.583	Very High Change
Comfort Seeking Advice	4.49	0.714	Very High Change
Collaboration & Teamwork	4.38	0.797	Very High Change
Mentoring by Experienced Colleagues	4.33	0.860	Very High Change
Sense of Belonging	4.54	0.624	Very High Change
Respect & Value	4.60	0.664	Very High Change
Follow-up Support	4.50	0.700	Very High Change
Emotional & Moral Support	4.70	0.523	Very High Change
Supportive Professional Relationships	4.66	0.652	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.53		Very High Change

Teachers reported very high changes in interpersonal relations, particularly in their sense of belonging and collaboration with colleagues. The overall mean of 4.53 reflects positive shifts in how teachers perceived their relationships with colleagues and administrators in the public sector. Higher ratings in emotional support and collegial respect indicate that teachers feel welcomed and valued within their new environments. In contrast, slightly lower ratings for mentoring and collaboration suggest that structured support mechanisms may not be consistently implemented. This aligns with Schlossberg's Transition Theory, which emphasizes the role of support systems in successful adaptation. These findings imply that interpersonal support played an important role in teachers' adjustment, although formal mentoring systems may still need strengthening, which is consistent with research emphasizing the importance of administrative and collegial support in shaping teachers' professional adjustment and job satisfaction (Sebullen & Jimenez, 2024).

5. Work Conditions

Work conditions focused on teachers' perceptions of their work environment, workload, access to resources, and support. Teachers reported significant improvements in work conditions after transitioning to public schools, although class sizes remained a challenge.

Table 8

Extent of Changes in Work Conditions

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Manageable Workload	4.38	0.771	Very High Change
Class Size for Teaching	4.06	1.079	High Change
Access to Materials & Resources	4.37	0.832	Very High Change
Supportive Classroom Environment	4.30	0.876	Very High Change
Manageable Documentation	4.39	0.935	Very High Change
Reasonable Workload Expectations	4.25	0.898	Very High Change

Adequate Teaching Equipment	4.24	1.045	Very High Change
Balanced Teaching & Prep Time	4.32	0.977	Very High Change
Administrative Support for Reports	4.46	0.727	Very High Change
Handling Schedule Demands	4.49	0.793	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.33		Very High Change

The overall mean of 4.33 highlights improvements in classroom resources and administrative support. Improvements in structural support do not fully compensate for classroom-level challenges, particularly workload and class size. This suggests that improvements in structural support did not fully remove classroom-level pressures, particularly those related to workload and instructional demands, a pattern also observed in recent studies on teacher effectiveness and well-being in resource-constrained school settings (Sayman et al., 2025; Polinar & Gemota, 2025).

6. Work Assignments

Work assignments assessed changes in teaching load, additional duties, and overall role clarity. Teachers reported significant improvements in how their work was distributed, with a high degree of alignment between their training and assigned roles.

Table 9

Extent of Changes in Work Assignments

Item	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Fair Teaching Load Distribution	4.35	0.766	Very High Change
Understanding Tasks & Responsibilities	4.43	0.697	Very High Change
Reasonable Additional Duties	4.11	0.974	High Change
Confidence in Assigned Roles	4.32	0.760	Very High Change
Balanced Workload for PD	4.38	0.784	Very High Change
Alignment with Training & Experience	4.37	0.795	Very High Change
Confidence & Competence via Orientation	4.41	0.813	Very High Change
Fair Distribution of Non-Teaching Duties	4.34	0.826	Very High Change
Overall Mean	4.34		Very High Change

Teachers perceived a very high extent of change in work assignments, with particularly high mean scores for fair teaching load distribution ($M = 4.35$) and alignment with training and experience ($M = 4.37$). These findings indicate that teachers generally felt more confident and satisfied with how work was assigned and aligned with their professional backgrounds. The results also suggest positive perceptions of role clarity and professional fit after transitioning to public schools. However, the lower rating for reasonable additional duties ($M = 4.11$) indicates that expanded responsibilities continued to contribute to workload pressure. The variation across indicators further suggests that while expectations were generally clear, task distribution was not always fully balanced. Overall, the findings show that role clarity was achieved to a considerable extent, but role expansion remained a key challenge, particularly in relation to non-teaching responsibilities, a pattern also noted in recent studies on teachers moving from private to public schools (Ostia & Celesio, 2025). From a Maslowian perspective, this suggests that while basic and security needs are met, higher-level needs such as work-life balance and well-being remain unmet.

Table 10

Thematic arrangement of teacher transition from private to public schools

Categories	Subcategories
Challenges Encountered During Transition	Bureaucratic and Administrative Hurdles Instructional and Classroom Challenges Cultural and Relational Shifts Personal Expectations and External Pressures Economic and Logistical Pressures
Opportunities During the Transition	Enhanced Professional Development and Job Security Mentorship and Peer Collaboration Improved Financial Stability
Coping Strategies During the Transition	Time Management and Adaptability Emotional Support and Seeking Guidance Professional Learning and Continuous Improvement

Implications on Instructional Practices and Well-being

Adjustments to Instructional Practices Work-Life Balance and Well-being

Key Recommendations for Transition Support Plan

Teacher Training and Support Emotional and Psychological Support Cultural and Classroom Integration Parent and Community Engagement Workload and Well-being

The interviews deepened the survey results by showing that teachers experienced the transition as a mix of structural gain and day-to-day adjustment. On the one hand, participants emphasized the attractiveness of the public-school system because of stability, compensation, and career development.

As one teacher put it, *"The biggest change for me was the job security. In public schools, I felt more secure about my job"* (R7). Another explained that the public-school system provided "stability, both in terms of job security and opportunities for professional growth" (R12). These accounts clarify why pay and benefits and job security ranked highest in the survey and are consistent with local evidence that teachers are often pulled toward the public sector by more stable employment conditions (Bergas et al., 2022; Ostia & Celesio, 2025). On the other hand, teachers described the transition as operationally demanding. Bureaucratic routines, documentation, and classroom scale surfaced repeatedly. One participant noted, *"In the public school system, there were more formal procedures and documentation requirements, which were initially overwhelming"* (R2). Another stated, *"Managing 55 students at once, especially with varying needs, has been a huge challenge"* (R10).

Teachers also pointed to resource constraints, commute difficulties, and delayed initial salary release as stressors. These narratives explain why work conditions and work assignments ranked lowest in the quantitative results and echo broader findings that administrative complexity, workload, and school context shape teachers' adjustment and retention (David & Santos, 2023; Guarino et al., 2022; Orbeta et al., 2022).

The interviews also showed that transition quality depended heavily on relationships. Teachers appreciated emotional and collegial support, but they did not always receive systematic mentoring. One participant said, *"A senior teacher took me under her wing and helped me navigate everything from lesson planning to classroom management strategies"* (R7), while others described feeling isolated during the early months when guidance was inconsistent. This helps explain the strong survey results for interpersonal relations alongside the comparatively lower score for mentoring by experienced colleagues. The pattern supports the argument that supportive leadership and collaborative culture matter, but informal goodwill should not be mistaken for an institutionalized induction structure (Haveman et al., 2024; Sebulen & Jimenez, 2024).

Coping strategies were pragmatic and relational. Teachers relied on time management, adaptability, peer consultation, and continuous professional learning. One teacher shared, *"Over time, I adapted by improving my organization and time management skills"* (R1), while another reported joining workshops to adjust to new curricular and instructional demands. Interviewees also linked the transition directly to instructional practice and well-being. Larger classes, diverse learners, and heavier paperwork required pedagogical adjustment, yet the same conditions sometimes strained work-life balance. These findings resonate with Schlossberg's emphasis on coping resources and with recent work on teacher stress and peer support in public-school settings (Janairo & Capellan, 2024; Leithwood et al., 2022).

Table 11

Joint display of quantitative patterns, qualitative explanations, and implications

Quantitative Pattern	Qualitative Explanation	Theoretical Reading	Implication for the Support Plan
Highest domain means were in pay and benefits (M = 4.61) and job security (M = 4.57).	Teachers repeatedly described public schools as more stable, better compensated, and more supportive of long-term career planning.	Herzberg highlights compensation and security as hygiene factors, while Maslow explains the appeal of safety and stability needs.	Provide early orientation on salary processing, tenure rules, promotion pathways, and benefits to strengthen perceived security from the start.

Work conditions (M = 4.33) and work assignments (M = 4.34) ranked lowest among the six domains.	Interviewees described heavy documentation, larger classes, uneven resources, and numerous additional tasks.	The transition improved structural conditions but did not fully resolve day-to-day work strain, showing that hygiene gains can coexist with operational burden.	Audit class size, paperwork load, and non-teaching duties; prioritize resource support for schools receiving new transferees.
Interpersonal relations remained strong (M = 4.53), but mentoring by experienced colleagues was the lowest item in that domain (M = 4.33).	Teachers often received emotional support informally, but not all schools had a consistent mentoring structure.	Maslow points to belonging needs, while Schlossberg emphasizes support as a core transition resource.	Institutionalize a first-year mentoring program instead of relying on voluntary collegial help.
Higher variability appeared in items tied to fairness, transparency, class size, and equipment (SDs around 1.00 or higher).	Accounts showed that transition quality differed by school, leadership responsiveness, and local resource conditions.	Schlossberg suggests that the success of transition depends on situation and support, not on the transfer event alone.	Use targeted, school-specific transition diagnostics rather than one-size-fits-all induction.
Teachers relied on time management, peer guidance, and professional learning to cope.	Participants adapted by organizing workloads, seeking support, and attending workshops to recalibrate their instruction.	Schlossberg's coping and strategy dimension is visible in teachers' adaptive responses.	Combine technical onboarding with psychosocial support, coaching, and continuous professional development.

Taken together, the findings show that teacher transition is best understood as a balance between structural gains and operational burdens. The strongest quantitative gains clustered around compensation, benefits, and employment stability, and the interviews confirmed that these were major reasons teachers valued the move. This pattern is consistent with Herzberg's argument that material and structural conditions reduce dissatisfaction and with Maslow's view that workers first seek security and stability before higher-order needs can be pursued.

However, the study also shows that structural improvement did not automatically produce smooth adaptation. Lower ratings for work conditions and assignments, combined with interview accounts of bureaucracy, larger classes, and uneven support, indicate that the public-school transition can remain difficult at the level of daily practice. Theoretically, this matters because it shows that hygiene gains and safety needs may be met while teachers still experience strain in belonging, esteem, and professional efficacy.

Schlossberg's transition lens is especially useful in explaining why the process was uneven. Teachers who had supportive colleagues, accessible leaders, and workable coping strategies adapted more successfully than those who faced inconsistent guidance, delayed salary release, or difficult logistics. In this sense, the transition was not shaped only by the transfer itself, but by the surrounding support environment. The study's novel contribution is therefore not simply that public schools were perceived more positively, but that the quality of transition depended on whether structural gains were matched by organized induction, mentoring, and school-level support.

From a policy standpoint, the findings suggest that teacher mobility should not be treated solely as a recruitment issue. Public schools may successfully attract teachers from private institutions, but retention and well-being require active transition management. Without onboarding, mentoring, and workload support, the same system that attracts teachers through security and compensation can also burden them through bureaucratic and classroom pressures. This is the central implication of the proposed Transition Support Plan.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the transition from private to public schools in Silay City is generally advantageous, but uneven in lived experience. Teachers reported meaningful gains in pay and benefits, job security, administrative clarity, and collegial support, making public school employment more stable, attractive, and professionally affirming. These quantitative patterns were reinforced by qualitative accounts showing that teachers valued the greater financial security, stronger employment protection, and wider professional development opportunities available in the public school system.

At the same time, the transition was not without difficulty. Teachers had to adjust to more formal bureaucratic systems, larger class sizes, heavier documentation requirements, and limited instructional resources. These conditions reshaped classroom

practice by demanding greater adaptability, stronger classroom management, and more deliberate time management. They also affected teacher well-being, particularly when compounded by travel demands, delayed salary release, and inconsistent school-level support.

Taken together, the findings show that teacher transition is not simply a matter of moving to a better-paying or more secure workplace; it is a complex professional adjustment process that requires institutional support to be fully sustainable. While the study was limited to self-reported data from teachers in one school division, and the findings should therefore be interpreted cautiously in other contexts, it nevertheless provides important local evidence for school leaders, human resource personnel, and division policymakers.

Ultimately, the significance of this study lies in its demonstration that the success of teacher transition depends not only on the structural advantages of public school employment, but also on the systems that help teachers adapt to new demands. By showing how stability and opportunity can coexist with strain and adjustment difficulties, the study offers a stronger basis for designing responsive onboarding, mentoring, workload support, and psychosocial interventions. In this way, the study contributes not only to the local understanding of teacher mobility in Silay City, but also to the broader effort to strengthen teacher retention, professional well-being, and the quality of public education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the development and implementation of a Transition Support Plan is recommended to provide teachers transitioning to public schools with structured, sustained, and context-responsive support. At the school level, this plan should include a structured 30-60-90 day onboarding and induction process that orients transitioning teachers to reporting systems, classroom expectations, school policies, documentation routines, and local procedures. Newly transitioned teachers should also be provided with trained mentors and peer-support buddies during their first year to support adjustment through regular check-ins, classroom observation, instructional assistance, and guidance on practical or emotional concerns. Schools should further strengthen transition-focused instructional support by offering coaching on classroom management, differentiated instruction, curriculum alignment, contextualized teaching, and relationship-building with diverse learners. In addition, workload distribution, non-teaching assignments, and access to instructional resources should be reviewed to reduce overload and ensure adequate support. Teacher well-being should likewise be prioritized through psychosocial support mechanisms such as adjustment check-ins, peer-support sessions, stress-management activities, and referral pathways for transition-related difficulties.

At the division and policy levels, standardized transition guidelines for teachers should be established to promote consistency across receiving schools. These may include a transition handbook, induction checklist, orientation programs, and standard reporting guide. Administrative systems should also be strengthened to ensure timely salary processing on the first three months and smoother transition-related coordination through early monitoring of requirements, tracking of appointment and payroll timelines, regular status updates, and responsive action on delays. Furthermore, parent and community engagement mechanisms should be enhanced to support newly assigned teachers through orientation activities, improved school-home communication, and coordinated community assistance for learner and school adjustment. Finally, transport and placement-related burdens, particularly in hard-to-reach assignments, should be addressed through more responsive placement considerations and locality-based or transport support where feasible.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest related to this study.

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